

**A CLINICAL STUDY TO EVALUATE THE EFFICACY OF RASNADI TAIL
MATRABASTI IN KASHTARTAVA - A REVIEW ARTICLE**

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ABSTRACT

Dysmenorrhea is the most common gynecological problem faced by Women during their adolescence and also in reproductive age which Causes significant discomfort and anxiety for the women. In modern Medicine dysmenorrhea is treated by oral contraceptive pills, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, antispasmodic, analgesics etc. This Treatment may relieve symptoms of dysmenorrhoea but it does not Address the root of the problem. Long term use of these causes side Effects. So to minimize these complications, an attempt is made to find Out safe, potent, cost effective remedy from Ayurveda for the Management of *Kashtartava*. In Ayurveda *Kashtartava*, term which is Being used for the condition where in a women may suffer with pain During menstruation. Pain is the main feature of *Kashtartava*, so it has Strong relation with Vata Dosha. For the management of this vitiated Vata, treatment that effect direct on the place of Vata should be selected Therefore by administering Basti to normalize vitiation of Vata and Proper measures to correct the *Agnivikara* should be the prime Objectives of the treatment. Keeping this point in view, the present Clinical trial, a clinical study to evaluate efficacy of “Rasnadi Tail”Matra-Basti” in the management of *Kashtartava* with special Reference to Primary Dysmenorrhea was taken. Rasnadi Tail Matra-Basti due to the properties of *Anulomana* and *Vatahara* may it Effectively brings down the *Pratiloma Gati* Vata which is mentioned in A.S.Utt. 39/29 for *Udavartini Yonivyapad*, which is one of the main disease Conditions compares with *Kashtartava* (Primary dysmenorrhoea). Results were assessed on the basis of improvement in the subjective Parameters. The study reveals that patients of *Kashtartava* after Treatment showed significant improvement in chief complaints, from the Above trial it is clear that Rasnadi Tail Matra-Basti can be used as a Safe and effective therapeutic agent in the management of *Kashtartava*.

KEYWORDS: Dysmenorrhea, *Kashtartava*, *Vatadosha*, *Matrabasti*.

INTRODUCTION

Dysmenorrhea is critical global health issue In reproductive age women, as it causes frequent Short-term work and school absenteeism and has a Significantly negative effect on daily activities. Dysmenorrhoea is defined as painful menstruation So as to incapacitate day to day activities. Primary Dysmenorrhea is extremely common, especially Among adolescents. Primary dysmenorrhea refers To menstrual pain without pelvic pathology. The Prevalence of primary dysmenorrhea was 85.4% of These, 28.5% had mild, 38.1% moderate and 18.8% Severe dysmenorrhea pain. In Ayurveda, *Kashtartava* is a broad term which covers all Problem and ailments that a woman may suffer During or around menstruation. It includes both Primary and secondary types of dysmenorrhea. For The present study, only primary dysmenorrhoea is taken with *Kashtartava* to exclude the pathological cases, but, in fact, no disease can be primary According to Ayurvedic principles, as each and Every disease has its certain pathogenesis. Still it Makes the study easier and the data

can be Analysed easily, if a single type origination of Disease is taken under consideration. *Acharya Charaka* has mentioned that *Yoniroga* can't occur Without vitiation of *Vata*. As *Vata* is main causative Factor it should be treated first. According to Ayurveda, pain is an indication of *Vata Vikriti –Vaataadrite Nasti Ruja*. Pain is the main feature of *Kashtartava*, so it has strong relation with *Vata Dosha*. According to *Acharya Sushruta*, *Apana Vayu* And *Vyana Vayu* are mainly responsible for *Artava Utpatti*. Normal menstruation is the function of The *Apanavata*. For the production of *Artava*, *Apana* and *Vyana* work in coordination with each Others. *Vyana Vayu* has control over the muscles Which brings about actions such as contraction, Relaxation, extension, flexion etc. Contraction, Relaxation of the uterus and its related organs is the Function of *Vyana Vayu*, after which *Artava* is Expelled out by *Anulomana kriya* of *Apana Vayu*. If Women have any difficulty in menstruation it Indicates *Apana* and *Vyana Vatadushti*. So *Kashtartava* is considered as a *Tridoshaja Vyadhi* With *Vata* predominance especially

due to Derangement of Apana and Vyana Vata. Basti has Being mentioned as one of the best therapeutic Procedure for alleviation of vitiated Vata. Out of All Sthanas of Vata the Pakvadhan is dominant and Basti can be considered as the closest path to reach Pakvashaya than other treatment procedures. Matra Basti is a type of Anuvasana Basti and the Simplest type of Basti. So it is selected for the Present study due to its indication in any season, at Any age, without much restriction. In addition Agnivikara induces vitiation of Apana Vata since the Three Vayus- Parana, Apana and Samana, located Normally in their respective places initiate and Preserve the metabolic power of the body. The Selected drug is Vatashamaka and correct the Agnivikara mentioned by the classics and Rasnadi Taila Matra -Basti due to the properties of Anulomana and Vatahara may it effectively brings Down the Pratiloma Gati Vata which is mentioned in A.S.Utt. 39/29[12] for Udavartini Yonivyapad which is One of the main diseases conditions compares with Kashtartava (Primary dysmenorrhoea).

DRUG FOR THE PRESENT STUDY

For the present study “Rasnadi Taila Matra Basti” was used. The formulation was Prepared Authentic Ayurved pharmacy according to Classical textual mode of preparation of oil.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

1. To study etiopathogenesis of Kashtartava as per The classical literature.
2. To evaluate the therapeutic efficacy of Rasnadi Taila Matra Basti in the management of Kashtartava.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Etiology

Ayurvedic concept of pain related to Kashtartava

Kashtartava is a disease of reproductive tract (Yoni Roga) situated in the pelvic region. This region consider as one of the main place of Vatadosha. AcharyaCharaka has mentioned none of the gynecological disease can be arise without affliction of aggravated Vata. By this it shows that disease Kashtartava shows strong relationship with Vatadosha by its origin place and the system it belongs to. It is well known that without association of Vata there cannot be pain.

Kashtartava

Kashtartava (dysmenorrhoea) is not Separately described as a disease. But there are many Diseases in which Kashtartava is considered and described As a symptom.

Nirukti

The term Kashtartava is made of two words –Kashta and Artava. Kashta: Painful, difficult, troublesome, ill, forced, wrong, Unnatural, a bad state of thing.

Artava

Belonging to reasons, period of time, menstruation. Thus, the word Kashtartava can be expressed as- “Kashthena Muchyati Iti Kashtartava” i.e., the condition Where Artava is shaded with great difficulty and pain is Termed as “Kashtartava”.

Hetu

वातल आहार चेष्टाया वातलायाः समीरणः ।
विवृद्धो योनिम आश्रित्य योनेः तोदं सवेदनम् ॥
स्तम्भ पिपीलिका सृष्टिम इव कर्कशतां तथा ।
करोति सुप्तिम् आयासं वातजान् च अपरान् गदान् ॥
सा स्यात् स शब्द रुक् फेन तनु रूक्ष आर्तव अनिलात् ॥
च.चि. 30 ॥
वातला कर्कशा स्तब्धा शूल निस्तोद पीडिता ॥ सु.3.38/11 ॥

Ayurveda says that women of vat prakruthi when consume diet and indulges on other vat aggravating factor then vat get vitiated kashtartava in which rasdhatushay create general weakness and causes oligomenorrhea associated with dysmenorrhoea when we go through all condition samanya nidan the general etiological factor of any kashtartava are found as mithya ahar vihar, artava, bijadusti, daiva prakopa etc.

Sampraptighataka

Dosha – Vata Pradhana Tridosha.

Vata – Vyana, Apana; Pitta – Ranjaka, Pachaka; Kapha as

Anubandhita Dosha ; Dhatu – Rasa, Rakta, Artava;

Upadhatu – Artava; Agni – Jatharagni, Rasagni,

Raktagni; Srotasa – Rasa, Rakta and Artavavaha Srotasa;

Srotodushti - Sanga and Vimargagamana;

Rogamarga –Abhyanaga; Sthana Samshraya –

Garbhashaya; VyaktiSthana – Garbhashaya.

DISEASE REVIEW

Concept of Kashta (Pain) In Ayurveda in Relation to Kashtartava

Without *vata* there can not be any pain. *Vata* is the main responsible factor, though other *Doshas* Only be present as *Anubandhi* to it. So, pain is produced Due to vitiation of alone *Vata Dosh* or in combination With other *Doshas*. *Sushruta* has described symptoms as roughness, Stiffness, acute pain and pricking pain. In this condition Pain is more in comparison to other *Yonivyapad*. (Gynaecological disorders) Of *Vata*.

Sannipatika Yonivyapad. There is burning sensation and pain in Vagina with yellowish and white unctuous vaginal Discharges *Udavarta Yonivyapad*. *Charaka* says that the Uterus is seized with pain, pushes the *Raja* (menstrual Blood) upwards and then discharges with great difficulty And pain. The lady feels comfort after discharging the Menstrual blood. *Sushruta* has described it to be Characterized by painful frothy menstruation, associated With other *Vatika* pain. *Indu* has added discharge of Clotted blood. *Yogaratanakara* has added the discharge Of frothy menstrual blood associated with *Kapha* with difficulty.

MODERN REVIEW

Definition of Menstruation

Menstruation is a function peculiar to women and the Higher apes. It may be defined as a “periodic and cyclic Shedding of pregestational endometrium accompanied by Loss of blood”. It takes place at approximately 28 days Interval between the menarche and menopause. Menstruation is the visible manifestation of cyclic Physiologic uterine bleeding due to shedding of the Endometrium following invisible interplay of hormones

Mainly through Hypothalamic pituitary-ovarian Endometrial axis.

DEFINITIONS OF DYSMENORRHEA

The term dysmenorrhoea refers to painful menstruation. Dysmenorrhoea is a cramp labour-like pain in the lower Abdomen that radiates to upper abdomen, waist and Thighs and is sometimes accompanied by systemic Symptoms like nausea, vomiting, diarrhoea, headache and dizziness.

Types of dysmenorrhea

There are two types of Dysmenorrhea

1. Primary dysmenorrhoea- The pain associated to Ovulation.
2. Secondary dysmenorrhoea- The pain associated With ovulatory cycles caused by a demonstrable Pathology.

DRUG REVIEW

Drug -Gokshur

"गोधुर्को मुत्रकृच्छ्रनिलहराणाम"।

(च.सू.२४)

Drug	Gokshur
Latin Name	Tribulus Terrestris. Linn
English Name	Puncture Vine
Marathi Name	Gokhru
Family	Zygophyllaceae
Ras	Madhur
Vipak	Madhur
Virya	Shita
Guna	Guru, Snigdha
Karma	Vatghna, Pittashamak
Part used	Phal

Drug-vasa

“वासायां विद्यमानायामाशायां जीवितस्य च । रक्तपित्ती क्षयी कासी किमर्थमवसीदति”¹(वृ.मा.)

Drug	Vasa
Latin Name	Adhatoda Vasica (Nees)
English Name	Malbar nut
Marathi Name	Vasa
Family	Acanthaceae
Ras	Tikta, Kashaya
Virya	Katu
Vipak	Shita
Guna	Laghu
Karma	Kafpitta sanshodhan
Part used	Patra

Drug – Rasna

“रसना वातहरणाम्”¹(च.सु.२५)

Drug	Rasna
Latin Name	Pluchea lanceolata
English Name	Lesser galanga
Marathi Name	Rasna
Family	Composite
Ras	Tikta
Virya	Katu
Vipak	Ushna
Guna	Guru, kafvat nashak
Part used	Patra,root

DISCUSSION**Mode of action of Matra Basti on Kashtartava**

Matra Basti has both local and systemic Effects. It causes *Vatanulomana* Thereby Normalizing *Apana Vata*. Mode of action of *Matra Basti* is defined in Ayurvedic classics very well. Acharya have explained its mode of action on Ayurvedic principles of *Dosha* and *Dosha-Dushya Sammurchhana*. Acharya *Sushruta* says that the *Virya* of *Basti* administered through the *Basti* Reaches the whole body through the channels (*Srotas*) as the active principles in the water when Poured at the root of the tree reaches the whole Plant. This definition explains how *Basti* acts on Whole the body after reaching in the gastrointestinal tract. Spasm caused by vitiated *Apana* and *Vyana Vayu* causing obstruction to the flow of Menstrual blood is the general underlying Pathology. Tail enters to the *srotas* and removes the *Sankochana* (Spasm) by virtue of its *Snigdha Sukshama Vyavayi* and *Vikashi* etc., fast spreading Nature. *Basti Dravya* normalizes the function of *Vata* By pacifying it after reaching all over the body. Its Contents act through their different chemical Constituents to restore the normal menstrual Physiology and thus, relieve pain during Menstruation. *Basti* can be affect on *Kashtartava* by Following mechanisms; improves overall nutrition Status of body, improves intestinal health and Absorption, nourishing the system, increasing the Immunity by detoxifying the system, and by action Of active principle of drug it breaks the pathology. Thus, *Basti* will act not only the pain, but the entire Whole the clinical picture of

Kashtartava (physical & Mental symptoms) of body by normalizing the Functions of *Vata*.

Concept of Matrabasti on Kashtartava

According to all Acharya *Basti* is a unique form of treatment modality. It expels the vitiated *Doshas* rapidly as well as it nourishes the body. *Basti* is the best choice of treatment for *Vatadosha* and *vata* associated with *kapha* and *pitta*. *Matrabasti* is a type of *SnehaBasti* i.e. *Anuvasana Basti*, described in the classics. According to Acharya Charaka, *Matrabasti* is Recommended for daily use in persons emaciated by over work, over exertion, load lifting, Way-faring, and riding or indulgence in women, in debilitated persons as well as in those afflicted with *Vatadisorder*.

“रसना श्रष्टां वृषकैः पिबेच्छूले भृतं पयः”¹(च.चि.३०/५६)

Acharya Charaka have mentioned .*Rasna* (root) *Gokshura* (fruit) and *Vasaleaves*.in Management of *Yoni shula* .these drug are helps in *Vatanuloman* by Diminishing *Margavordha samprapti*. *Rasna* is best Analysis and anti Inflammantary herb.(best *Vastashamak* Drug). It Alleviates Pain in the abdomen. Pelvis and pelvis organs (uterus, fallopian tubes, ovaries And vagina).*Gokshura* is also good anti-inflammatory herb.it is good diuretic (*mutravirecharyk*)Therefore it is reduce the edema associated with female reproductive system and pelvis. It also cleanses the urinary bladder and good for reproductive system. *Vasa* is best medicine in bleeding disorder. It helps in checking excess. Bleeding Disorder. It helps in checking excess bleeding and associated pain in excessive. Vaginal Bleeding, dysmenorrhea and PID (pelvic Inflammatory disease).

EFFICACY OF MATRABASTI

In *Vataj Vikara* according Acharya *Charaka Basti* is Consider as *ardhachikitsa* (half of therapeutics) according charka Acharya we can give *Matrabasti* in all persones. while taking *Matrabasti* person can take the normal diet And do the regular activities. *Matrabasti* can be given in any seasons. The dose of *Matrabasti* is equal to minimum dose of *snehapana*. *Matrabasti* promotes strength and can administer very easily it helps in voiding Of stool it causes nourishment and cures disease cause by *vat*. Hence *Matrabasti* well treat in *vataj vikar* in this case study the effect of *Matrabasti* with 60 ml *Rasanadi tail* Acharya *Charaka* have mentioned *Rasna* (root) *Gokshura* (fruit) and *Vasa*(leaves). In Management of *Yonishula*. These drug are helps in *Vatanuloman* by diminishing *Margavordha samprapti*. *Rasna* is best Analysis and anti Inflammantary herb.(best *Vastashamak* Drug). It alleviates Pain in the abdomen. Pelvis and pelvis organs (uterus, fallopian tubes, ovaries and vagina). *Gokshura* is also good anti-inflammatory herb.it is good diuretic (*mutravirecharyk*)therefore it is reduce the edema associated with female reproductive system and pelvis. It also cleanses the urinary bladder and good for reproductive system. *Vasa* is best medicine in bleeding disorder. It helps in checking excess bleeding disorder. It helps in checking excess bleeding and associated pain in

excessive. Vaginal bleeding, dysmenorrhea and PID (pelvic Inflammatory disease).

CONCLUSION

The disease "Kashtartava" is not described in classics as An individual disease entity. Even then it is a symptom of Various Yoni *vyapad* specially *Udavarta* (Upward Movement of Vayu with retention of stool and urine), *Vatala*, *Sannipataja* etc. It is Tridosha Vyadhi with Vata Predominance. Ayurveda viewing Primary Dysmenorrhea As a *Doshic* imbalance that can potentially be impacted Through balanced living and appropriate diet, herbal Supplements, exercise, routine, Yoga, meditation, as well As nourishing inputs through all five senses. Ayurveda Being a holistic medicine offers potential remedies which are proved beyond doubt in solving the problem in Gynaecological disorders successfully. *Rasnadi Taila Anuvasana Basti* per rectally act As Shodhana therapy effective in relieving Kashtartava. The effect of *Rasnadi Taila* Matrabasti had prolonged effect in Relieving cardinal and associated symptoms. Further it helps to reduce the possibility of Recurrence which was evident on follow-up.

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